

Data for the article "Metal-centred states control carrier lifetimes in transition metal oxide photocatalysts"

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This document contains a brief description of the datasets used to create the figures in the main text and in the Supplementary Information.

Main text

Figure 1

F1a_Absorbance_{material}.csv: Absorbance of Cr₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, and Co₃O₄ thin films, recorded using UV-Vis spectroscopy

- Columns: Energy (eV), Absorbance

F1b_Band_structure_{material}.csv: Band structure of Cr₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, and Co₃O₄, calculated using density functional theory

- Columns: k-distance, Eigenvalue (eV)
- In each file, different bands are appended vertically and are separated by one empty row
- Because the [sumo-bandplot](#) code used to generate the band structures does not output the orbital assignment (i.e., O2p and metal 3d), the input files needed to reproduce this output are included separately (see *F1b_Band_structure_input.zip*)

F1b_Band_structure_input.zip: Input files for the band structure plots and calculations

- Data structure: The .zip file contains one subfolder per material. In each subfolder, the input files follow the folder structure (split-0*) recommended by [sumo-bandplot](#)
- The files needed to reproduce the band structure plots are the *vasprun.xml* and *KPOINTS* files. Further VASP input/output files (*INCAR*, *POSCAR*, *POTCAR* and *vasp.out*) are included for further clarity, in case reproduction of the DFT calculations is necessary

Figure 2

F2a_TA_spectra_Fe2O3_LMCT.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption spectra for Fe₂O₃ upon LMCT excitation

- First column: Probe energy (eV)
- Subsequent columns: Absorbance difference signals (ΔA) probed at the times indicated in picoseconds, calculated by subtracting the absorbance in the ground state from that in the excited state
- Excitation energy: 3.10 eV (400 nm)
- Photogenerated carrier density: $9.6 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$
- Sample under continuous nitrogen flow

F2b_TA_spectra_Co3O4_LMCT.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption spectra for Co₃O₄ upon LMCT excitation

- First column: Probe energy (eV)
- Subsequent columns: Absorbance difference signals (ΔA) probed at the times indicated in picoseconds, calculated by subtracting the absorbance in the ground state from that in the excited state
- Excitation energy: 2.76 eV (450 nm)
- Photogenerated carrier density: $2.7 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$
- Sample under continuous nitrogen flow

F2c_TA_spectra_Cr2O3_LMCT.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption spectra for Cr₂O₃ upon LMCT excitation

- First column: Probe energy (eV)
- Subsequent columns: Absorbance difference signals (ΔA) probed at the times indicated in picoseconds, calculated by subtracting the absorbance in the ground state from that in the excited state
- Excitation energy: 3.76 eV (330 nm)
- Photogenerated carrier density: $9.0 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$
- Sample under continuous nitrogen flow

F2d_TA_spectra_Cr2O3_LF.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption spectra for Cr₂O₃ upon LF excitation

- First column: Probe energy (eV)
- Subsequent columns: Absorbance difference signals (ΔA) probed at the times indicated in picoseconds, calculated by subtracting the absorbance in the ground state from that in the excited state
- Excitation energy: 2.70 eV (460 nm)
- Photogenerated carrier density: $1.4 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$
- Sample under continuous nitrogen flow

F2_Raw_data.zip: Raw transient absorption datasets from which the panels of this figure are produced.

- Data organization: Each subfolder corresponds to one material, containing the TA datasets collected in the visible and near-infrared probe ranges. All datasets have been corrected for chirp and background.
- Data layout: Each file contains the probe wavelength in the first column and the time in the first row. The rest of the dataset are the transient absorption difference signal amplitudes (ΔA) at each wavelength-time point. The first datapoint (first row, first column; set to 0) only serves to comply with the shape of the 2d array and can be ignored.

Figure 3

F3a_TA_kinetics_Co3O4.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption kinetics for Co₃O₄ as a function of laser fluence

- Data layout: The first column contains the probed times in picoseconds, while the second column contains the corresponding absorbance difference signals divided by the used photogenerated carrier density ($\Delta A/n$; unit: cm^3). Each subsequent pair of columns repeats this pattern for data recorded at a different photogenerated carrier density.
- Excitation energy: 1.68 eV (740 nm)
- Probe energy: 1.13 eV (1100 nm), averaged over the 1050 - 1150 nm window

- Sample under continuous nitrogen flow

F3b_TA_kinetics_Cr2O3.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption kinetics for Cr₂O₃ as a function of laser fluence

- Data layout: The first column contains the probed times in picoseconds, while the second column contains the corresponding absorbance difference signals divided by the used photogenerated carrier density ($\Delta A/n$; unit: cm^3). Each subsequent pair of columns repeats this pattern for data recorded at a different photogenerated carrier density.
- Excitation energy: 3.40 eV (365 nm)
- Probe energy: 1.13 eV (1100 nm), averaged over the 1050 - 1150 nm window
- Sample under continuous nitrogen flow

F3c_TA_kinetics_Fe2O3.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption kinetics for Fe₂O₃ as a function of laser fluence

- Data layout: The first column contains the probed times in picoseconds, while the second column contains the corresponding absorbance difference signals divided by the used photogenerated carrier density ($\Delta A/n$; unit: cm^3). Each subsequent pair of columns repeats this pattern for data recorded at a different photogenerated carrier density.
- Excitation energy: 3.10 eV (400 nm)
- Probe energy: 1.13 eV (1100 nm), averaged over the 1050 - 1150 nm window
- Sample under continuous nitrogen flow

F3d_TA_kinetics_BiVO4.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption kinetics for BiVO₄ as a function of laser fluence

- Data layout: The first column contains the probed times in picoseconds, while the second column contains the corresponding absorbance difference signals divided by the used photogenerated carrier density ($\Delta A/n$; unit: cm^3). Each subsequent pair of columns repeats this pattern for data recorded at a different photogenerated carrier density.
- Excitation energy: 3.54 eV (350 nm)
- Probe energy: 1.13 eV (1100 nm), averaged over the 1050 - 1150 nm window
- Sample under continuous nitrogen flow

F3e_TA_kinetics_normalized.csv: Comparison of the ultrafast transient absorption kinetics for different materials at a photogenerated carrier density of ca. $1 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$

- Data layout: The first column contains the probed times in picoseconds, while the second column contains the corresponding normalized absorbance difference signals (normalized ΔA). If the structured signal component contributes to the recorded signal, it is subtracted as described in the Supplementary Figure 23. Each subsequent pair of columns repeats this pattern for a different material.
- Probe energy: 1.13 eV (1100 nm), averaged over the 1050 - 1150 nm window
- Samples under constant nitrogen flow (all except TiO₂) or argon atmosphere (TiO₂)
- The following datasets are used for this comparison:
 - TiO₂: 3.49 eV (355 nm) excitation, $6.6 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ photogenerated carrier density
 - BiVO₄: 3.54 eV (350 nm) excitation, $8.9 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ photogenerated carrier density
 - Fe₂O₃: 3.10 eV (400 nm) excitation, $9.6 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ photogenerated carrier density

- Cr2O3: 3.40 eV (365 nm) excitation, $2.6 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ photogenerated carrier density
- Co3O4: 1.68 eV (740 nm) excitation, $1.6 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ photogenerated carrier density

F3f_TA_amplitude_1ps.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption amplitudes at 1 ps as a function of laser fluence for different materials

- Data layout: The first column contains the photogenerated carrier density in cm^{-3} , while the second column contains the corresponding absorbance difference signals divided by the used photogenerated carrier density ($\Delta A/n$; unit: cm^3). Each subsequent pair of columns repeats this pattern for a different material.
- Experimental conditions as described above for the individual materials

F3_Raw_data: Raw transient absorption datasets from which the panels of this figure are produced.

- Data organization: Each subfolder corresponds to one material, containing TA datasets collected at different laser fluences. All datasets have been corrected for chirp and background.
- Data layout: Each file contains the probe wavelength in the first column and the time in the first row. The rest of the dataset are the transient absorption difference signal amplitudes (ΔA) at each wavelength-time point. The first datapoint (first row, first column; set to 0) only serves to comply with the shape of the 2d array and can be ignored.

Figure 4

F4a_Light_harvesting_potential.csv: Light harvesting potential of different photoabsorbers

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: Materials
 - Column 2: d-occupancy (d0 - d10)
 - Column 3: Absorption onset of the material (eV)
 - Column 4: Photons absorbed (%)
- To calculate the number of photons absorbed, it is assumed that all photons with an energy above the absorption onset are absorbed (limit of a sufficiently thick film)
- For the solar spectrum, the "Direct+circumsolar" data provided at <https://www2.nrel.gov/grid/solar-resource/spectra-am1.5> is used

F4b_Half_lifetimes.csv: Half lifetimes of different photoabsorbers

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: Materials
 - Column 2: d-occupancy (d0 - d10)
 - Column 3: Half lifetime of reactive charges as determined from time-resolved measurements (ps)

Supplementary Information

SF1_XRD_Co3O4.csv: X-ray diffraction data for Co3O4

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: 2θ angle
 - Column 2: Experimental data
 - Column 3: Reference data (see SI for citation)

SF2_XRD_Fe2O3.csv: X-ray diffraction data for Fe₂O₃

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: 2θ angle
 - Column 2: Experimental data
 - Column 3: Reference data (see SI for citation)

SF3_XRD_Cr2O3.csv: X-ray diffraction data for Cr₂O₃

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: 2θ angle
 - Column 2: Experimental data
 - Column 3: Reference data (see SI for citation)

SF4_XRD_BiVO4.csv: X-ray diffraction data for BiVO₄

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: 2θ angle
 - Column 2: Experimental data
 - Column 3: Reference data (see SI for citation)

SF5_XRD_NiO.csv: X-ray diffraction data for NiO

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: 2θ angle
 - Column 2: Experimental data
 - Column 3: Reference data (see SI for citation)

SF6_XRD_CdO.csv: X-ray diffraction data for CdO

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: 2θ angle
 - Column 2: Experimental data
 - Column 3: Reference data (see SI for citation)

SF7_Co3O4_Raman.csv: Raman data for Co₃O₄

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: Wavenumber (cm⁻¹)
 - Column 2: Raman intensity (a.u.) for Co₃O₄ sample
 - Column 3: Raman intensity (a.u.) for blank quartz glass substrate
- Excitation wavelength: 633 nm

SF7_Co3O4_Raman_reference.csv: Digitized reference Raman data for Co₃O₄ (see SI for citation)

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: Wavenumber (cm⁻¹)
 - Column 2: Raman intensity (a.u.)
- Excitation wavelength: 532 nm

SF8_Fe2O3_Raman.csv: Raman data for Fe₂O₃

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: Wavenumber (cm^{-1})
 - Column 2: Raman intensity (a.u.) for Fe_2O_3 sample
 - Column 3: Raman intensity (a.u.) for blank quartz glass substrate
- Excitation wavelength: 633 nm

SF8_Fe2O3_Raman_reference.csv: Digitized reference Raman data for Fe_2O_3 (see SI for citation)

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: Wavenumber (cm^{-1})
 - Column 2: Raman intensity (a.u.)
- Excitation wavelength: 633 nm

SF9_BiVO4_Raman.csv: Raman data for BiVO_4

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: Wavenumber (cm^{-1})
 - Column 2: Raman intensity (a.u.)
- Excitation wavelength: 532 nm

SF9_BiVO4_Raman_reference.csv: Digitized reference Raman data for BiVO_4 (see SI for citation)

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: Wavenumber (cm^{-1})
 - Column 2: Raman intensity (a.u.)
- Excitation wavelength: 530 nm

SF10_CdO_Raman.csv: Raman data for CdO

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: Wavenumber (cm^{-1})
 - Column 2: Raman intensity (a.u.)
- Excitation wavelength: 532 nm

SF10_CdO_Raman_reference.csv: Digitized reference Raman data for CdO (see SI for citation)

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: Wavenumber (cm^{-1})
 - Column 2: Raman intensity (a.u.)
- Excitation wavelength: 532 nm

SF15_Tauc_fit_Co3O4_absorbance: Tauc plot data for Co_3O_4 at different temperatures

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: Energy (eV)
 - Columns 2-7: Tauc absorbance values $\alpha h\nu^2$ ($\text{eV}^2 \text{cm}^{-2}$), where each column corresponds to one temperature

SF15_Tauc_fit_Co3O4_parameters.csv: Tauc fit parameters for Co_3O_4 at different temperatures

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: Temperature (K)
 - Column 2: Bandgap (eV)
 - Column 3: Tauc slope from linear fit
 - Column 4: Tauc offset from linear fit

SF16_Tauc_fit_Cr2O3_absorbance: Tauc plot data for Cr2O3 at different temperatures

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: Energy (eV)
 - Columns 2-7: Tauc absorbance values $\alpha h\nu^2$ ($\text{eV}^2 \text{ cm}^{-2}$), where each column corresponds to one temperature

SF16_Tauc_fit_Cr2O3_parameters.csv: Tauc fit parameters for Cr2O3 at different temperatures

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: Temperature (K)
 - Column 2: Bandgap (eV)
 - Column 3: Tauc slope from linear fit
 - Column 4: Tauc offset from linear fit

SF17_Tauc_fit_Fe2O3_absorbance: Tauc plot data for Fe2O3 at different temperatures

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: Energy (eV)
 - Columns 2-7: Tauc absorbance values $\alpha h\nu^2$ ($\text{eV}^2 \text{ cm}^{-2}$), where each column corresponds to one temperature

SF17_Tauc_fit_Fe2O3_parameters.csv: Tauc fit parameters for Fe2O3 at different temperatures

- Data layout:
 - Column 1: Temperature (K)
 - Column 2: Bandgap (eV)
 - Column 3: Tauc slope from linear fit
 - Column 4: Tauc offset from linear fit

SF18{a-d}_TA_spectra_{material}.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption spectra for Fe2O3, Cr2O3, and Co3O4 upon LMCT excitation, as well as Cr2O3 upon LF excitation; analogous to the data presented in Figure 2, showing only data in the near-infrared probe range.

SF19_TA_spectra_Co3O4_excitation.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption spectra for Co3O4 upon excitation at different excitation energies

- Columns 1, 3, 5: Probe energy (eV)
- Columns 2, 4, 6: Corresponding absorbance difference signals (ΔA) probed at 0.3 ps, calculated by subtracting the absorbance in the ground state from that in the excited state
- Photogenerated carrier density: $\sim 2 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$
- Sample under continuous nitrogen flow

SF20_TA_kinetics_us-s.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption kinetics for Fe₂O₃, Cr₂O₃, and Co₃O₄ probed at microsecond to second time delays

- Columns 1, 3, 5: Time (s)
- Columns 2, 4, 6: Corresponding absorbance difference signals (ΔA), calculated by subtracting the absorbance in the ground state from that in the excited state
- Excitation energy: 3.49 eV (355 nm)
- Excitation fluence: 2.0 mJ cm⁻² for Cr₂O₃; 0.8 mJ cm⁻² for Co₃O₄ and Fe₂O₃
- Probe energy: 1.91 eV (650 nm) for Cr₂O₃; 2.25 eV (550 nm) for Co₃O₄ and Fe₂O₃
- Sample under continuous nitrogen flow

SF21_TA_spectra_5.7ns.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption spectra for Cr₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, and Co₃O₄ probed at 5.7 ns

- Columns 1, 3, 5: Time (s)
- Columns 2, 4, 6: Corresponding absorbance difference signals (ΔA), calculated by subtracting the absorbance in the ground state from that in the excited state; analogous to the 5.7 ns data presented in Figure 2

SF21_Absorbance_spectra_2nd_derivative.csv: Second derivatives of the absorbance spectra for Cr₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, and Co₃O₄.

- Columns 1, 3, 5: Probe energy (eV)
- Columns 2, 4, 6: Corresponding second derivative absorbance spectra

SF22a_TA_spectra_Fe2O3_temperature.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption spectra for Fe₂O₃, averaged between 1 ns and 6 ns, as a function of temperature

- Columns 1, 3, 5, etc.: Probe energy (eV)
- Columns 2, 4, 6, etc.: Corresponding absorbance difference signals (ΔA), calculated by subtracting the absorbance in the ground state from that in the excited state
- Photogenerated carrier density: $\sim 2 \times 10^{19}$ cm⁻³

SF22b_TA_spectra_Co3O4_temperature.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption spectra for Co₃O₄, averaged between 1 ns and 6 ns, as a function of temperature

- Columns 1, 3, 5, etc.: Probe energy (eV)
- Columns 2, 4, 6, etc.: Corresponding absorbance difference signals (ΔA), calculated by subtracting the absorbance in the ground state from that in the excited state
- Photogenerated carrier density: $\sim 2 \times 10^{19}$ cm⁻³

SF22c_TA_spectra_Fe2O3_fluence.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption spectra for Fe₂O₃, averaged between 1 ns and 6 ns, as a function of photogenerated carrier density (by tuning the laser fluence)

- Columns 1, 3, 5, etc.: Probe energy (eV)
- Columns 2, 4, 6, etc.: Corresponding normalised absorbance difference signals (ΔA), calculated by subtracting the absorbance in the ground state from that in the excited state, followed by normalisation via division by the average signal amplitude in the 560 - 590 nm probe range
- Temperature: 295 K
- Raw data are provided with Figure 3

SF22d_TA_spectra_Co3O4_fluence.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption spectra for Co₃O₄, averaged between 1 ns and 6 ns, as a function of photogenerated carrier density (by tuning the laser fluence)

- Columns 1, 3, 5, etc.: Probe energy (eV)
- Columns 2, 4, 6, etc.: Corresponding normalised absorbance difference signals (ΔA), calculated by subtracting the absorbance in the ground state from that in the excited state, followed by normalisation via division by the average signal amplitude in the 580 - 600 nm probe range
- Temperature: 295 K
- Raw data are provided with Figure 3

SF22_Raw_data: Raw transient absorption datasets from which panels a and b of this figure are produced.

- Data organization: Each subfolder corresponds to one material, containing TA datasets collected at different temperatures. All datasets have been corrected for chirp and background.
- Data layout: Each file contains the probe wavelength in the first column and the time in the first row. The rest of the dataset are the transient absorption difference signal amplitudes (ΔA) at each wavelength-time point. The first data point (first row, first column; set to 0) only serves to comply with the shape of the 2d array and can be ignored.

SF23a_TA_kinetics_Co3O4_temperature.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption kinetics for Co₃O₄, averaged between 1050 nm and 1150 nm, as a function of temperature

- Columns 1, 3, 5, etc.: Time (ps)
- Columns 2, 4, 6, etc.: Corresponding normalised absorbance difference signals (ΔA), calculated by subtracting the absorbance in the ground state from that in the excited state
- Raw data are provided with Supplementary Figure 22

SF23b_TA_kinetics_Cr2O3_temperature.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption kinetics for Cr₂O₃, averaged between 1050 nm and 1150 nm, as a function of temperature

- Columns 1, 3, 5, etc.: Time (ps)
- Columns 2, 4, 6, etc.: Corresponding normalised absorbance difference signals (ΔA), calculated by subtracting the absorbance in the ground state from that in the excited state

SF23c_TA_kinetics_Fe2O3_temperature.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption kinetics for Fe₂O₃, averaged between 1050 nm and 1150 nm, as a function of temperature

- Columns 1, 3, 5, etc.: Time (ps)
- Columns 2, 4, 6, etc.: Corresponding normalised absorbance difference signals (ΔA), calculated by subtracting the absorbance in the ground state from that in the excited state
- Raw data are provided with Supplementary Figure 22

SF23_Raw_data: Raw transient absorption datasets from which panel b of this figure is produced.

- Data organization: One Cr₂O₃ subfolder, containing TA datasets collected at different temperatures. All datasets have been corrected for chirp and background.
- Data layout: Each file contains the probe wavelength in the first column and the time in the first row. The rest of the dataset are the transient absorption difference signal amplitudes (ΔA) at each wavelength-time point. The first data point (first row, first column; set to 0) only serves to comply with the shape of the 2d array and can be ignored.

SF24a_Co3O4_kinetics_background_subtraction.csv: Background subtraction for the Co₃O₄ kinetic trace shown in Figure 3e.

- Columns 1, 3, 5: Time (ps)
- Column 2: Kinetic trace recorded at low fluence, from which the background is subtracted
- Column 4: High fluence trace, used to determine the background
- Column 6: Background, determined via fit to the high fluence trace and convolved with a Gaussian instrument response ($\mu = 0.1$ ps, $\sigma = 0.05$ ps)
- Probe energy: 1.13 eV (1100 nm), averaged over the 1050 - 1150 nm window

SF24b_Cr2O3_kinetics_background_subtraction.csv: Background subtraction for the Cr₂O₃ kinetic trace shown in Figure 3e.

- Columns 1, 3, 5: Time (ps)
- Column 2: Kinetic trace recorded at low fluence, from which the background is subtracted
- Column 4: High fluence trace, used to determine the background
- Column 6: Background, determined via fit to the high fluence trace and convolved with a Gaussian instrument response ($\mu = 0.1$ ps, $\sigma = 0.05$ ps)
- Probe energy: 1.13 eV (1100 nm), averaged over the 1050 - 1150 nm window

SF24c_Fe2O3_kinetics_background_subtraction.csv: Background subtraction for the Fe₂O₃ kinetic trace shown in Figure 3e.

- Columns 1, 3, 5: Time (ps)
- Column 2: Kinetic trace recorded at low fluence, from which the background is subtracted
- Column 4: High fluence trace, used to determine the background
- Column 6: Background, determined via fit to the high fluence trace and convolved with a Gaussian instrument response ($\mu = 0.1$ ps, $\sigma = 0.05$ ps)
- Probe energy: 1.13 eV (1100 nm), averaged over the 1050 - 1150 nm window

SF25a_NiO_absorbance.csv: Absorbance of a NiO thin film, recorded using UV-Vis spectroscopy

- Columns: Energy (eV), Absorbance

SF25b_TA_spectra_NiO.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption spectra for NiO

- First column: Probe energy (eV)
- Subsequent columns: Absorbance difference signals (ΔA) probed at the times indicated, calculated by subtracting the absorbance in the ground state from that in the excited state
- Excitation energy: 4.13 eV (300 nm)
- Laser fluence: 0.37 mJ cm⁻²
- Sample under continuous nitrogen flow

SF25c_TA_kinetics_NiO.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption kinetics for NiO as a function of laser fluence

- Data layout: The first column contains the probed times in picoseconds, while the second column contains the corresponding absorbance difference signals divided by the used laser fluence ($\Delta A/n$; unit: cm²). Each subsequent pair of columns repeats this pattern for data recorded at a different laser fluence.
- Excitation energy: 4.13 eV (300 nm)

- Probe energy: 1.13 eV (1100 nm), averaged over the 1050 - 1150 nm window
- Sample under continuous nitrogen flow

SF25_Raw_data: Raw transient absorption datasets from which panels b and c of this figure are produced.

- Data organization: One NiO subfolder, containing TA datasets collected at different laser fluences. All datasets have been corrected for chirp and background.
- Data layout: Each file contains the probe wavelength in the first column and the time in the first row. The rest of the dataset are the transient absorption difference signal amplitudes (ΔA) at each wavelength-time point. The first data point (first row, first column; set to 0) only serves to comply with the shape of the 2d array and can be ignored.

SF26a_CdO_absorbance.csv: Absorbance of a CdO thin film, recorded using UV-Vis spectroscopy

- Columns: Energy (eV), Absorbance

SF26b_TA_spectra_CdO.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption spectra for CdO

- First column: Probe energy (eV)
- Subsequent columns: Absorbance difference signals (ΔA) probed at the times indicated, calculated by subtracting the absorbance in the ground state from that in the excited state
- Excitation energy: 3.54 eV (350 nm)
- Laser fluence: 0.034 mJ cm^{-2}
- Sample under continuous nitrogen flow

SF26c_TA_kinetics_CdO.csv: Ultrafast transient absorption kinetics for CdO as a function of laser fluence, normalized to the average signal amplitude in the 1 - 2 ps time range

- Data layout: The first column contains the probed times in picoseconds, while the second column contains the corresponding absorbance difference signals divided by the used laser fluence ($\Delta A/h$; unit: cm^2). Each subsequent pair of columns repeats this pattern for data recorded at a different laser fluence.
- Excitation energy: 3.54 eV (350 nm)
- Probe energy: 2.40 eV (516 nm), averaged over the 506 - 526 nm window
- Sample under continuous nitrogen flow

SF26_Raw_data: Raw transient absorption datasets from which panels b and c of this figure are produced.

- Data organization: One CdO subfolder, containing TA datasets collected at different laser fluences. All datasets have been corrected for chirp and background.
- Data layout: Each file contains the probe wavelength in the first column and the time in the first row. The rest of the dataset are the transient absorption difference signal amplitudes (ΔA) at each wavelength-time point. The first data point (first row, first column; set to 0) only serves to comply with the shape of the 2d array and can be ignored.